

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

CRITICAL THINKING OF FUTURE TEACHERS AS AN IMPORTANT COMPONENT OF TEACHER PROFESSIONAL CULTURE

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Abstract

This article focuses on the critical thinking of students in vocational training in high school. The author analyzes one of the rapidly developing areas of reform of the system of modern higher education as a focus on the development of critical thinking of the person, which implies the existence of skills of reflection about their own mental activity, the ability to work with concepts, judgments, conclusions, issues, and development of analytical, forecasting activities problematic vision, the search for alternative and innovative forms, means and methods for facilitating management to meet the challenges.

Keywords: *critical thinking, forecasting activities, modern higher education.*

In modern society, the need for developing individuals capable not only of reproducing existing norms and traditions but also of independently analyzing, evaluating, drawing conclusions, making adequate and objective decisions, and self-developing in personal and professional terms while rejecting their own stereotypes in activities and behavior is becoming increasingly relevant. At the same time, the requirements for professional competencies of specialists and their level of personal responsibility for the professional decisions they make are increasing, which is associated with the trend towards building an open, democratic society characterized by high mobility, creativity, ability to innovate, and criticism.

Every person is capable of thinking, and this is what allows humanity to develop. When we think, we usually process the information we receive based on what we already know and make our judgments. No one can deny that all people go through this process many times a day. We can question the result of our thinking process, that is, our judgments. We often make mistakes in our judgments, and this is where critical thinking can help us.

One of the actively developing directions of reforming the system of modern higher education is the focus on the development of critical thinking of the individual, which implies the presence of skills for reflection on one's own mental activity, the ability to work with concepts, judgments, conclusions, questions, the development of analytical and forecasting abilities, problem vision, the search for alternative and innovative forms, means and methods that contribute to rational decision-making on tasks and problems, as well as the ability to evaluate similar opportunities for others. This makes the development of this type of thinking an important condition for the formation of a competitive personality of a teacher.

Many researchers, such as I.S. Litvinova, O.M. Semenova, M.A. Tarasova, T.V. Kharlampeva, and others, have studied critical thinking and consider it an important component of professional education.

Research has shown that the modern education system should be built on providing students with the opportunity to reflect, formulate, and argue their own point of view based on knowledge of facts, laws, and regularities of science, as well as their own observations and the experience of others.

The development of students' critical thinking, as noted by A.V. Korzhuyev, V.A. Popkov, has a positive influence on the formation of the competence of future specialists and is recognized as a necessity of the modern education system [1; 2].

The presence of a high level of critical thinking skills contributes to the development of competencies necessary for effective educational and professional activities of teachers in universities, such as systemic and interpersonal competencies. Therefore, if the development of critical thinking affects the competence of a teacher, then to enhance this positive influence, the process of developing critical thinking should be based on the specifics of professional activity.

Currently, in higher education pedagogy, the problem of the professional and personal development of university teachers is actively being developed. Works by P.A. Shatskov, G.V. Shchagina, I.A. Romanova and others consider issues of forming value orientations and professionally significant qualities of a teacher.

Some scholars define critical thinking as "social thinking" or "socially-directed thinking", which exists in society and seeks to improve society by rethinking its problems and drawing conclusions about their solutions. Taken together with the above, this provides a basis for believing that the development of this type of

thinking will contribute to the improvement of professional university training of specialists in the pedagogical field.

Implementation of critical thinking by teachers in their educational and professional activities also contributes to rational planning of their own educational and professional activities and prioritization of their functional responsibilities, improving the quality of students' perception and assimilation of educational material. Therefore, it improves the quality of education of future teachers in the process of acquiring specialized knowledge, skills, and abilities, obtaining the most reliable and up-to-date, professionally-oriented information, and developing alternative solutions to educational and professional problems.

An analysis of philosophical and psycho-pedagogical literature has shown that the problem of developing critical thinking in modern science is very interesting and relevant. It has been established that "critical thinking" is, first and foremost, a type of thinking with a specific critical orientation. The category of "thinking" belongs to interdisciplinary concepts and is the subject of study of various sciences such as philosophy, psychology, pedagogy, physiology, sociology, etc., and its examination is carried out in a philosophical, psychological, pedagogical context.

The analysis of the views of philosophers (Bacon, G. Hegel, I. Kant, Plato, Socrates, B. Spinoza, and others) shows that in philosophy, "thinking" is considered as a phenomenon characterized by objectivity and having several forms, the ability to independently comprehend reality, create, solve, and act according to certain rules, a necessary element of knowledge, and an independent essence of nature, not dependent on humans or humanity.

In psychology, thinking is one of the actively developed categories. Different psychological schools approach this phenomenon differently, such as associationists (D. Hartley, E. Darwin, Spencer, and others), representatives of another school (K. Bühler, Marber, J. Watt, and others), behaviorists (E. Gazzaniga, J. Watson, and others), and cognitive psychologists (A. Newell, H. A. Simon, and others).

Existing interpretations of "thinking" reveal various aspects of this concept as a developing ability to solve various tasks and transform reality in a purposeful way, aimed at revealing hidden aspects of reality that are not immediately observable (L. S. Vygotsky, P. Ya. Galperin, A. N. Leontiev, S. L. Rubinstein, D. B. Elkoinin, and others).

Thus, in modern psychological science, the category of "thinking" is disclosed in a broad sense as active cognitive activity, as well as an internal process of planning and regulating external activity, and in a narrow sense as a process of solving various tasks or problems.

In many psychological studies, the concept of "thinking" is considered identical to the concept of "intelligence," but intelligence plays a role as a concept that unites an individual's cognitive and creative abilities. Thinking, in turn, accumulates an individual's intellectual abilities to solve various problems and tasks. Therefore, the process and result of an individual's

thinking depend on their intellectual abilities, but intelligence develops thanks to the improvement of the quality of cognitive and creative abilities. In other words, the development of thinking is simultaneously the process of developing intelligence.

If psychology studies thinking as a mental process, then pedagogy is interested in thinking as an individual's ability to acquire knowledge and the process of its formation and development. Analysis of pedagogical research on the problem of formation and development of thinking allows us to note that scientists study thinking as a way of solving problems (its basis was laid by A. Distervig, H. Pestalozzi, J.-J. Rousseau and received further development in the theory of problem-based learning); develop ways and methods of forming and developing professionally-oriented types of thinking in the process of preparing future specialists (V. Slastenin, T. Kudryavtsev, V. Medvedev, E. Osipova, and others). Also, pedagogy pays special attention to the formation and development of various types of human thinking with the aim of improving the quality of their social adaptation, assessing various phenomena, solving problems and tasks, acquiring new knowledge, etc. (T. Badanova, D. Bragina, N. Vysotchikina, T. Polyakova, and others).

In the Pedagogical Dictionary, thinking is understood as "mediated reflection of the external world, which is based on impressions from reality and enables a person, depending on the knowledge, skills, and abilities they have acquired, to correctly operate information, successfully build their plans and programs of behavior." Along with the term "thinking," the concepts of "mental development" and "mental upbringing" are often used in pedagogy. Although these two concepts are close in meaning, they have some significant differences. "Mental upbringing" is a process aimed at the subject of upbringing, while "mental development" is a process of changes inherent in the subject of pedagogical influence. At the same time, mental upbringing largely determines mental development, contributes to it, but this happens only if the regularities and possibilities of the mental development of the subject of pedagogical influence are taken into account. Therefore, in pedagogy, great attention is paid to studying the features of the ontogenesis of personality thinking.

The concept of "criticism" is mainly used in two meanings: as a negative attitude towards something and as the expression of an opinion about something based on analysis of facts. In pedagogy, the concept of "criticism" is crucial for the direction of the thinking process and relates to the process of analysis and drawing conclusions. Therefore, in a broad sense, criticism should be regarded as an analysis of the essence, regularities, and results of phenomena with the aim of making an objective judgment.

Developing critical thinking skills in students during their professional training in university is necessary because at this age stage, there is a higher speed of working memory and attention switching, effective solution of verbal-logical problems, making it a favorable period for purposeful development of critical thinking.

In their professional activities, a teacher performs educational, organizational, prognostic, preventive, organizational-communicative, and other functions in such areas of activity as: protecting the human rights proclaimed by the UN Convention to life and healthy development, education and free expression of their views, protection against any kind of discrimination, etc.; establishing normal interpersonal relationships in the team. In order to successfully perform the above functions, a teacher must have a certain level of development of analytical, prognostic, reflective skills.

Analyzing the professional activities of a teacher and their professional and personal qualities shows that the content of a teacher's work is determined by the functions they perform, and the requirements for their professional and personal qualities are based on the fact that they exert a great influence on the personality of the student during their professional activities, and the effectiveness of the development of these qualities significantly affects the success of their professional pedagogical work.

The concept of "critical thinking" originated within formal logic, however, critical thinking has a practical orientation, which allows it to be interpreted as a form of practical logic that is considered within and dependent on the context of reasoning and individual characteristics of the reasoning subject. One of the most important features of critical thinking is that it enables individuals to analyze and construct reasoning based on logic and objectivity, to argue their conclusions, to acquire knowledge that forms the basis of their professional activities, and to reassess their own prejudices and stereotypes in behavior, activities, and thinking. An analysis of the characteristics of critical thinking contained in the definitions of various authors shows that the main ones are purposefulness, organization, rationality, reflexivity, analyticality, and logicity.

Critical thinking of a future teacher aimed at solving problems and pedagogical tasks may contain errors that arise during the analysis of initial data, which can be detected by analyzing the process of critical thinking itself. However, the analytical component of a teacher's critical thinking allows tracking positive and negative changes, as well as identifying errors and inaccuracies in solving professional problems. Logical thinking, which is present at every stage of critical thinking, is responsible for correcting the consequences of errors and taking into account changes in circumstances that arise during a teacher's critical thinking process.

The rationality of a teacher's critical thinking helps prevent subjectivity in making certain decisions within the given task. The organization of a teacher's critical thinking has several features related to the specifics of their professional activity. It should initially take into account the non-static nature of the object of pedagogical influence, which may cause some circumstances to change. When there are multiple factors that are not always amenable to analysis, providing a clear and precise prediction of the final result or the result of a critical thinking stage is challenging.

Reflectiveness, as a characteristic of a teacher's critical thinking, emphasizes the importance of their professional and personal experience in solving the

tasks at hand. By reflecting on the problems during the process of critical thinking, the teacher consciously applies their personal experience to draw conclusions regarding the ways to solve them and to gain new experience. Reflection becomes a process of mutual, mirrored reflection between subjects, the content of which is the reproduction and recreation of each other's features. This is also important because while working with students, the teacher not only solves their problems but also teaches them how to solve problems independently. The experience gained by the teacher during the problem-solving process, when perceived reflectively, contributes to an increase in their level of professionalism.

The characteristics of critical thinking in a teacher that have been discussed above are interrelated: dominating at different stages, they reflect the process of critical thinking.

Critical reflection and resolution of professional problem situations is a process that is largely creative, often involving the search for innovative, alternative ways, means, and forms, and therefore cannot be based solely on theoretical knowledge and research and pedagogical technologies acquired by students. Sharing the point of view of A.S. Sharov and I.A. Sharshov on the necessity of complementing the intellectual and creative components for the effective professional and creative self-development of future specialists, it can be stated that critical and creative types of thinking are interrelated: creative problem solving is impossible without understanding its essence, and critical thinking itself is not a way to solve a problem [4;5].

However, critical thinking plays an important role in the process of implementing practically all the main functions of a teacher (organizational, educational, diagnostic, prognostic, organizational-communicative, etc.).

Critical thinking of a teacher is a professionally oriented type of thinking that determines the reflective-analytical position of a specialist. It is manifested in the vision and analysis of problematic aspects of the interaction between the "person-person" and "person-society" systems, in the evaluation of the adequacy of measures taken to perform professionally significant tasks in the field of pedagogical activity, readiness to abandon stereotypes and search for logically-alternative solutions.

Indicators of the development of critical thinking include the ability to plan and organize educational and professional activities, the ability for self-analysis and self-development, the ability to assess and verify the process of solving professionally significant problems, proficiency in working with professional-oriented information and its sources, the ability to solve non-standard professionally-oriented situations, the ability to establish cause-and-effect relationships between different phenomena, and the ability to search for alternative ways to achieve set goals.

The goal of the pedagogical technology for developing critical thinking skills in the process of professional training in university is to create conditions for the formation of a progressive level of critical thinking and its active use in the educational and professional

activities of students. The integrity and interconnection of the characteristics and indicators of the development of a teacher's critical thinking skills ensure a substantive unity, which is achieved through the flexible use of various forms and methods of joint activities between students and teachers.

In conclusion, it is important to emphasize that critical thinking skills are necessary for everyone. We must be aware of our own shortcomings, biases, prejudices, as well as the sources of our worldview, paradigms, and information channels that we use when processing new information. Critical thinking is not an instant action, it requires effort and courage to admit our own mistakes. Teaching critical thinking is also not an instant process. State and non-state educational institutions should strive to develop critical thinking skills among students, and such a desire may require us to change our approach to teaching. It is very important

that we, acting for the benefit of all humanity, take the necessary steps to increase the number of people in the world who think critically.

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